

Effect of plant derivatives on brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) nymph emergence on rice

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We tested nine plant derivatives for their inhibitory effect on BPH and WBPH nymphs. Forty-day-old potted IR20 plants were sprayed with 1% oils of neem *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, pinnai *Calophyllum inophyllum* L.,

pungam *Pungamia glabra* L., and illupai *Madhuca longifolia* Macbr var. *latifolia* Boxb. cheval; 2% seed extracts of neem, pinnai, pungam, and illupai; and 5% neem cake extract, using a baby hand sprayer. Treated plants were confined separately with five gravid females of BPH and of WBPH in three replications. Nymphal emergence was assessed daily for 1 wk after spraying.

All plant derivatives were effective in reducing emergence of planthoppers (see table). Highest BPH reduction was with 5% neem cake extract, followed by 2% pungam seed extract. Highest WBPH reduction was with 5% neem cake extract, followed by 2% neem seed kernel. □

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Treatment	BPH		WBPH	
	Nymph emergence (no.)	Decrease from control (%)	Nymph emergence (no.)	Decrease from control (%)
1% neem oil	96 c (8.26)	31.7	93 e (9.60)	12
1% pinnai oil	118 d (10.23)	15.4	118 f (10.86)	0.6
1% pungam oil	89 c (9.42)	22.2	68 d (8.20)	25
1% illupai oil	107 cd (9.65)	20.2	96 e (9.76)	11
2% neem seed kernel	64 b (7.99)	34	43 b (6.59)	40
2% pinnai seed extract	97 cd (9.68)	20	108 f (10.4)	5
2% pungam seed extract	30 a (5.47)	55	53 c (7.26)	34
2% illupai seed extract	83 c (9.11)	25	74 d (8.60)	21
5% neem cake extract	24 a (4.86)	60	30 a (5.46)	50
	147 e (12.1)		120 g (10.93)	
LSD (P = 0.05)	1		1	

^aMean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are transformed values. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Using rice straw bundles to conserve beneficial arthropod communities in ricefields

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Population densities of spiders and other beneficial arthropods decreased greatly after rice harvest because of disruption of their habitats. Harvesting, irrigation, plowing, and harrowing activities leave vegetation only along bunds and field edges for refuge of these natural enemies of rice

pests. Conservation of these beneficial forms during crop-free periods is important to ensure adequate numbers to recolonize fields when the rice crop is established.

We evaluated using bundles of rice straw as habitats for arthropod predator and prey communities during crop-free periods in irrigated rice.

The bundles were prepared by arranging rice straw into cone-shaped tents about 30 cm in diameter at the bottom. One tent was placed in the center of each of 24 plots in a newly harvested field. Plots were 10 × 7 m. Arthropods were collected using a vacuum sampler (D-vac) 5 and 10 d after placing tents in the field. Samples were placed in vials containing 70% alcohol solution and brought to the laboratory for sorting and counting.

Significantly more arthropods were collected 10 d after placing the tents in the field (Fig. 1). Natural enemies collected included coleopterans--*Stilbus* spp., *Micraspis*, *Ophionea*; orthopterans--*Metioche*, *Anaxipha*; hymenopterans--*Telenomus* spp., ants, *Anagrus*, *Oligosita*, *Goniozous*, *Mymarid*, *Bracon*, and *Elasmus*. Spiders were the most abundant group. The most common spider species were *Callitrichia formosana* and *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Fig. 2). There were

1. Arthropods collected from rice straw bundles placed in ricefields after harvest. IRRI, 1989.